

Resilient and Adaptive Supply Chains for Capability-based Manufacturing as a Service Networks

Grant Agreement No. 101138782

Deliverable 6.1

Dissemination and Communication Plan

**Funded by
the European Union**

Project title	RAASCAMAN - Resilient and Adaptive Supply Chains for Capability-based Manufacturing as a Service Networks
Grant Agreement number	101138782
Funding scheme	Call: HORIZON-CL4-2023-TWIN-TRANSITION-01 Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2023-TWIN-TRANSITION-01-07
Project duration	1 September 2024 – 31 August 2027 (36 months)
Project coordinator	DFKI – Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz GmbH
Deliverable number	6.1
Title of the deliverable	Dissemination and Communication Plan
WP contributing to the deliverable	WP6
Deliverable type	R – Document, report
Dissemination level	PU – Public
Due submission date	28 February 2025 (M6)
Actual submission date	
Partner(s)/Author(s)	CTU - Eva Doležalová, Tereza Pospíšilová
Internal reviewers	RPTU - Patrick-Antoni Kremser
Final approval	

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History of changes		
When	Who	Comments
02/12/2024	Eva Dolezalova (CIIRC CTU)	Document created, initial structure outlined
08/01/2025	Eva Dolezalova (CIIRC CTU)	Structure refined, parts of texts (target groups)
14/01/2025	Tereza Pospisilova (CIIRC CTU)	Communication and dissemination drafted and elaborated
20/01/2025	Eva Dolezalova (CIIRC CTU)	Adjustment of the structure of the document – new chapters
30/01/2025	Eva Dolezalova (CIIRC CTU)	Introduction chapters finalised
06/02/2025	Heike Leonhard (DFKI)	Planned events
06/02/2025	Eva Dolezalova (CIIRC CTU)	Chapters in Communication improved
12/02/2025	All	Planned events + process comments
19/02/2025	Eva Dolezalova (CIIRC CTU)	Improvements of particular chapters in Dissemination and completion of the document
20/02/2025	Patrick-Antoni Kremser (DFKI)	Internal review
24/02/2025	Eva Dolezalova (CIIRC CTU)	Comments from the review reflected in the prefinal version (v05)
27/02/2025	Eva Dolezalova (CIIRC CTU) based on input from Netcompany Intrasoft	Reference to the Exploitation Strategy added and document finalised (v07)

Confidentiality	
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Executive Summary

This document outlines a comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy for the RAASCEMAN project as well as a reference to its exploitation strategy, uniting both aspects into a single framework to effectively address the project's goals, activities, and results. The strategy has been designed to ensure that the RAASCEMAN initiative is communicated and disseminated in a way that maximizes its impact and fosters understanding among a diverse range of audiences, including stakeholders from the industry, research communities, policymakers, and the general public.

1 Introduction

This document has been elaborated within the RAASCAMAN's Work Package 6 on *Exploitation, dissemination, and communication* (Task 6.1 / Communication and Dissemination Support and Activities) and it defines a sound strategy for the development of effective communication and dissemination tools, measures and activities. The goal is to create and continuously increase awareness about the project and secure dissemination of the project objectives, results, opportunities, best-practices and contributions to standardisation, targeting industrial and scientific communities and private and public stakeholders.

The **communication** aspect of this strategy centers on raising awareness about the RAASCAMAN project, particularly its technological advancements and efficiency. It aims to make the project accessible to the public and stakeholders through a variety of channels, including traditional and social media, public events, and outreach activities. Through these efforts, RAASCAMAN not only showcases how EU funding is being effectively utilized but also highlights its potential to contribute to long-term sustainability and innovation in the manufacturing domains.

Dissemination activities focus on ensuring that the results of RAASCAMAN are shared with key stakeholders who can benefit from the project's outcomes. These activities target industrial partners, policymakers, and research institutions, offering them the tools and knowledge to adopt and build upon RAASCAMAN's solutions. The dissemination strategy is closely tied to the exploitation and practical implementation of the project's outcomes, ensuring that stakeholders can utilize the results in ways that foster further innovation, partnerships, and sustainability.

1.1 Methodology

The communication and dissemination efforts of the RAASCAMAN project are structured to ensure effective outreach, engagement, and impact. The methodology for this strategy is structured around several key elements. Firstly, the content to be communicated and disseminated focuses on the project's assets, such as its innovative approaches to creating a decentralized MaaS network and its validation in industrial Use-Cases. Secondly, the identification of target audiences ensures that messages are tailored to the needs and interests of specific groups, whether they are industry professionals, policymakers, or the general public. Thirdly, the tools and channels used include both digital platforms and in-person engagements to maximize outreach and visibility. Lastly, the implementation timeline ensures that activities are conducted in a timely manner, with ongoing monitoring and evaluation to adapt to emerging needs and challenges. These core frameworks will guide the project's communication and dissemination activities throughout its lifecycle. All these activities must be designed to be adaptable, responsive, and collaborative, emphasizing the creation of meaningful relationships with diverse stakeholders and fostering the wide-scale adoption of the project's outcomes. Following main stages must be achieved:

1) **Awareness**

Raising the awareness and engagement is closely tied with the communication activities described in the Communication Strategy. It consists of continuous informing of the clearly defined groups of stakeholders about the project results and impacts, paying special attention to promoting the project achievements, highlighting its excellence and its significance within the European manufacturing sector.

2) **Community and confidence building**

Engage key stakeholders (including policymakers, industrial partners, research institutions, and the general public) to ensure broad-based collaboration and feedback. It is necessary to address each particular target group with the information tailored to its interests and through the channels suiting best the purpose of information delivery. Support of the running projects, partners and organisations shall be made in a transparent way with clear emphasis on the benefits that RAASCAMAN brings to the stakeholders. This will help to foster sustainable partnerships that drive long-term impact beyond the project's lifespan.

3) **Utilisation of the project results**

Growing from the stakeholder's understanding and engagement in long-term perspective in ways that promote knowledge transfer and enhance industrial resilience and innovation. Crucial is to promote the adoption and

scaling of RAASCCEMAN's technological advancements, with a particular focus on the decentralized Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS) network and its validation within real-world use cases.

Structure of the strategy:

- What (project assets and results)
- To whom (target groups)
- By what means (tools, channels for each target group)
- When (action plan)
- Monitoring and evaluation of quantitative targets
- Ad-hoc and on-demand actions – agile approach when needed

1.2 Purpose of this document

The purpose of this document is to establish a clear and structured approach to promoting the RAASCCEMAN project and disseminating its results. By focusing on a decentralized Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS) network aimed at strengthening European supply chains, the communication and dissemination efforts emphasize the project's contributions to industrial resilience and innovation. The strategy also provides opportunities for engaging stakeholders in meaningful dialogue, ensuring that feedback and collaboration shape the project's outcomes and improve its relevance in addressing real-world challenges.

This document is based on the RAASCCEMAN Description of Action which outlined the main parameters and elements of the communication and dissemination plan (chapter 2.2 of the project proposal). This deliverable also builds on a previously submitted D1.1 Deliverable on Requirements and specifications (Lead: Flanders Make, submitted in M5), especially in terms of analysis and extraction of the main stakeholders and users and their requirements. It is also tightly linked to the deliverables on *Exploitation strategy, IP Management and Business Case*, Lead: Netcompany-Intrasoft to be delivered as D6.2 in M6, D6.3 in M18 and the final D6.4 in M36.

The factual impact assessment of C&D activities multiplying the RAASCCEMAN results with key and industrial stakeholders within the European innovation ecosystem will be delivered in M36 as a deliverable D6.5 *Report on Community Dissemination*.

Given the nature of the C&D activities and the environment in which they are implemented, this deliverable is designed as a living strategy, capable of adapting to the dynamic needs and agile approach of the project and the evolving expectations of its audiences. Regular updates will be made to reflect new developments, incorporate emerging opportunities, and address unforeseen challenges.

Thus, this document represents RAASCCEMAN's roadmap and vision for communication, dissemination and exploitation in the early stage of the project, and is based more on internal validation of the relevant stakeholders. To fully reflect this ever-changing scenario, D6.1 is only the first in a series of WP6 deliverables, which in later phases will be more focused on the project's key impact pathways and based on leveraging already proven knowledge and accelerating innovation and scaling-up efforts within the RAASCCEMAN's ecosystem.

2 Communication Strategy

2.1 About RAASCCEMAN

RAASCCEMAN aims at developing and testing a decentralized capability-based MaaS network creating resilience for European supply chains while enabling the human to make informed decisions in case of medium- and short-term disruptions. The technology developed in RAASCCEMAN will be implemented in two challenging Industrial use cases from the domains of automotive and bike manufacturing validating technical and economic viability of MaaS as well as and the interconnected pilot line use case demonstrating different tools developed in the project on a connected MaaS network.

2.1.1 Mission & Vision

The RAASCCEMAN project is dedicated to transforming supply chain resilience through innovative, decentralized solutions. By leveraging Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS) networks, digital twins, and circularity-driven practices, RAASCCEMAN empowers manufacturers to swiftly adapt to unforeseen disruptions, ensuring continuity and efficiency. Our mission is to enable companies to lower market barriers, embrace dynamic supply chain models, and drive sustainable, agile production. Through cutting-edge software tools, data exchange infrastructures, and a focus on European values, RAASCCEMAN will equip industries to future-proof their operations, while contributing to the growth of a resilient, interconnected European manufacturing ecosystem.

2.2 Key Communication Assets

RAASCCEMAN's assets and Unique Selling Propositions (USPs) provide a foundation for crafting targeted messages that address the specific needs and priorities of its audience. These messages should be clear, concise, and compelling, emphasizing the unique value of RAASCCEMAN solutions and the benefits of engaging with its ecosystem.

The project's communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategies shall be designed around these key assets and messages, showcasing its significance and contribution to technology, industry, and society. These elements will be utilized to maximize the visibility and impact of RAASCCEMAN's results.

Communication efforts will focus on delivering relevant, straightforward information to diverse audiences, emphasizing the project's broader effects on technology, competitiveness, and sustainability.

Key communication assets can be divided into the following thematic areas in terms of project implementation:

2.2.1 Core Facts and Objectives

- RAASCCEMAN's consortium including leading research organisations and also leading industrial manufacturers from six European countries.
- Unique interconnection of infrastructure of RAASCCEMAN partners that dispose of cutting-edge technological equipment in their industrial testbeds and labs.
- Clear articulation of RAASCCEMAN's mission and goals, emphasizing decentralized capability-based MaaS network that creates resilience for European supply chains while enabling the human to make informed decisions in case of medium- and short-term disruptions towards the increase of competitiveness of the European industry.
- Priority list of challenges tackled in RAASCCEMAN to increase the resilience of supply chains (as described both in DoA and D1.1):

Challenge 1: Common semantic representation

Challenge 2: Intra- and cross-factory communication based on standards and European values

Challenge 3: Enabling human decision maker to react to unforeseen events

Challenge 4: Enable companies to swiftly find suppliers and ensuring trust and reliability

Challenge 5: Enable companies to swiftly create quotes and adapting production

- Description of the use-cases (bike industry, automotive industry, interconnected pilot line) for testing and validation of technical and economic viability of MaaS approach.
- Objectives 1-8 as described in DoA/project proposal:
 - Obj. 1 – Actionable propositions for adapting supply chains or internal production and logistics based on reliable quantification and impact prediction of unforeseen events
 - Obj. 2 – Dynamic supply chain generation enabling resilience and self-adaptation of MaaS networks
 - Obj. 3 – Building Trust in MaaS networks auditing suppliers’ reliability and testing plausibility of offers
 - Obj. 4 – Dynamic planning and scheduling of production processes enabling companies to swiftly adapt logistics and production to varying external conditions
 - Obj. 5 – Dynamic assembly and disassembly to enable machines in the field level to adapt to unforeseen changes
 - Obj. 6 – Creating digital twins and infrastructure for supply chain and factory simulations and enabling trusted cross-company data exchange based on standards and European values
 - Obj. 7 – Validating technical and economic viability of MaaS
 - Obj. 8 – Proof the advantage of circularity using remanufactured goods as a local procurement alternative
- Focus on automation, resilience, and sustainability as core pillars of RAASCCEMAN’s strategic agenda.
- Focus on realistic value chains where manufacturers can quickly adapt to changes in demand, respond to supply chain disruptions, and optimize their production processes.
- Focus on increased flexibility and resiliency to provide manufacturers with the ability to quickly reconfigure their production lines and adapt to changing market conditions, maintaining high levels of product quality and safety.
- Focus on customization to meet the specific needs of manufacturing OEMs, enabling them to create production lines that are tailored to their products and processes.

2.2.2 Use Cases and Pilots

The RAASCCEMAN use cases and pilots elaborated on the main goals can showcase the principles of RAASCCEMAN solutions to better understand the final results and outcomes of the project even before their completion. In communication, use cases will also contribute to the identification of the potential stakeholders and broader audiences with the R&D challenges tackled by RAASCCEMAN and transpose them to their particular situations.

Specific RAASCCEMAN Use Cases:

- Use-Case 1: Bike industry – Focus on medium-term unforeseen events
- Use-Case 2: Automotive industry – Focus on short-term unforeseen events
- Use-Case 3: Interconnected pilot line use-case based on a product that is manufactured across the pilot lines

The RAASCCEMAN use cases can be translated to the following high-level sector-independent use cases as outlined in D1.1:

- Use case 1: React to unforeseen events
- Use case 2: Select a new supplier
- Use case 3: Create Product Digital Twin (PDT)
- Use case 4: Replanning
- Use case 5: Describe manufacturing service

2.2.3 Broader Impacts of RAASCCEMAN Findings

- **Technological Development:** Showcasing RAASCCEMAN’s contributions to cutting-edge AI, robotics, and Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS) solutions.
- **Competitiveness:** Positioning RAASCCEMAN as a driver of European manufacturing competitiveness by enhancing flexibility, agility, and responsiveness.
- **Resilience:** Highlighting innovations that strengthen supply chain resilience, reduce dependency on external disruptions, and ensure continuous operation in complex environments.

- **Sustainability:** Demonstrating how RAASCCEMAN technologies promote energy efficiency, resource optimization incl. remanufacturing, and environmentally conscious practices in manufacturing processes.
- **Economic Growth:** Communicating RAASCCEMAN's contributions to creating economic value through technological advancements and the adoption of Industry 4.0 principles.

2.3 Target Groups

RAASCCEMAN aims to address multiple stakeholders across various sectors, ensuring broad engagement and fostering innovation in manufacturing resilience through advanced AI and Industry 4.0 technologies. The following outlines the key target groups for RAASCCEMAN's activities, with specific focus on their relevance, communication channels, and tailored content.

2.3.1 Industrial Stakeholders and Innovation Ecosystems

These are the primary users and beneficiaries of the RAASCCEMAN project's outcomes. They will be crucial in ensuring the successful uptake and integration of the solutions developed. These groups will benefit from MaaS (Manufacturing as a Service), remanufacturing capabilities, and integration of digital twins.

- **Prospective end-users:** European manufacturing companies (of any size - large manufacturers, small- and medium-sized enterprises/SMEs, midcaps) and supply chain managers across several sectors, mainly from manufacturing sectors such as automotive or machinery, especially those with complex and dynamic supply chains that are searching for the availability of new tools leading to higher resilience and who request manufacturing service in form of a value-adding activity to manufacture a product.
- **Demand side:** Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM), high-end product manufacturers, customized products producers focusing on small batch sizes and medium-sized lot sizes; **Supply side:** Contract manufacturers, software service providers, companies in the supply chain network (component suppliers, assembly providers, tool suppliers, production managers), remanufacturing actors, procurement, process planning and product development organizations, homologation bodies and quality experts.
- **Supply chain and logistics service providers:** Companies that manage supply chains and offer digital solutions related to manufacturing processes, particularly those focusing on flexibility and outsourcing production in real-time.
- **European information and communication technologies (ICT) service sector and technology providers** (system integrators, incl. startups in the area) providing automation, digitalization, data management and other ICT services to the manufacturing industries. The project will contribute to widening and strengthening their service offering and on the other hand, they develop technologies that can be integrated into the RAASCCEMAN system, such as digital twins, supply chain optimization tools, and platforms for remanufacturing or 3D printing.
- **Innovation and start-up sphere and technology facilitators and clusters:** Technology providers and developers, system integrators and engineering, process data and quality monitoring providers, technology, software service providers and developers, and process optimisers.
- **Professional communities, industry associations and networks:** Industrial clusters, digital associations, EIT Manufacturing and their ecosystems provide networking opportunities for innovation in these sectors.
- **European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs):** A one-stop-shop for industries that offers digital services, consultancy, education, training and networking for companies. As they collaborate with each other, EDIHs assist in coupling with counterparts across the EU.

2.3.2 Scientific Community

RAASCCEMAN's focus on innovative digital solutions and manufacturing processes will interest academic researchers and institutions. Researchers and scholars working in fields such as computer science, industrial AI, automation, digital manufacturing and other Industry 4.0-related domains with linkage to the open-source community – both academics and non-academics, spin-offs or RTOs. They participate in the adoption of project outcomes and scientific advancements and test the project's value and impact, also providing feedback.

- Students and early-stage researchers:
- Specific group of the community that deserves special attention for their great potential for innovative approaches and also motivation to continue with their R&D activities.
- AI-driven Networks and Initiatives: European associations and innovation platforms, ADRA, Gaia-X, euRobotics, ELLIS, CAIRNE (former CLAIRE), EFFRA, IDSA and their ecosystems as well as European projects.

2.3.3 Policymakers and Professional Stakeholders

RAASCCEMAN’s solutions align with several key European strategic goals, especially around digitalization, sustainability, and supply chain resilience. Engaging with policymakers at national and EU levels is crucial for fostering wider adoption and ensuring alignment with EU policy. Also, standardisation bodies working on regulations related to industry and digital technologies as well as national and regional governments, such as ministries, regional councils, chambers of commerce, professional associations, and public sector organisations. They may be interested in how RAASCCEMAN’s approach to MaaS can impact local industries and improve supply chain stability in their regions.

2.3.4 Society and the General Public

While the direct benefits of RAASCCEMAN’s tools may be felt mostly within industries, the public will indirectly benefit from the more sustainable, flexible, and resilient products that result from RAASCCEMAN’s innovations. End consumers are exposed to the advances in the area of manufacturing resilience and ultimately benefit from better, more resilient products and services that come from the implementation of circular economy practices and the adaptability enabled by MaaS.

When communicating to the public incl. community organisations and individuals, the debates on benefits and known or unforeseen consequences of new technologies will contribute to a better understanding of the sustainability and resilience of products, and how innovation in manufacturing is leading to better-quality goods, greater efficiency and reduced environmental impact.

RAASCCEMAN recognizes the need for public awareness and acceptance of new technologies. Engaging with the general public will help highlight the innovations in manufacturing and their benefits for society, particularly in terms of sustainability, job creation, and economic development.

2.4 Tools and Channels

To effectively communicate with the identified target audiences for the RAASCCEMAN project, it is important to tailor the communication tools and channels to their specific needs, preferences, and the level of technical detail they require. By leveraging the following tools and channels, RAASCCEMAN can effectively reach and engage each of its target audiences, fostering collaboration, knowledge-sharing, and uptake of its innovative solutions.

2.4.1 Website

KPIs:	8 000 visits by the end of the project
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Since its launch in M3, the RAASCCEMAN website has served as the primary and comprehensive source of information about the project, acting as a hub for all stakeholders, including industrial partners, academics, policymakers, and the general public. The website has been designed to deliver clear, accessible, and engaging

content while highlighting the project's goals, activities, and results. It has been continuously updated to ensure relevance and maintain high user engagement.

Key Features and Content

- About RAASCCEMAN
 - A structured overview of the RAASCCEMAN project, duration, funding, objectives and core focus and innovation areas.
 - A dedicated section introducing the partners involved in RAASCCEMAN, including their roles and contributions. This emphasizes the collaborative and cross-sectoral nature of the project and its consortium.
 - Repository of documents incl. selected public deliverables.
- Research
 - Overview of main challenges tackled by RAASCCEMAN that the European manufacturing industry is facing nowadays.
 - Description of the main strategies of the RAASCCEMAN approach to tackle these research challenges.
- Use-Cases
 - A special section focused on the use-cases in automotive and bike industries as well as interconnected pilot line use-case developed as part of the project. These will include detailed descriptions supported by tutorials, training materials, and content such as infographics and videos.
- Results
 - This section will showcase RAASCCEMAN's publications, tangible outcomes, and innovative tools.
- News
 - Regular updates on the project's activities, media outputs, interviews, and major achievements. This section features the latest RAASCCEMAN-related developments to keep visitors informed. It will also include events such as workshops, conferences, and networking sessions. Visitors will be able to explore details of RAASCCEMAN's participation in industry events, access event materials, and view recordings from these activities.

User Experience and Accessibility

The RAASCCEMAN website has been designed to provide a seamless and user-friendly experience. Key elements include:

- Responsive Design: Ensuring compatibility with all devices, incl. tablets and smartphones.
- SEO Optimization: Ensuring high visibility of the website in search engine results for relevant topics such as AI in manufacturing, Industry 4.0 solutions, resilient supply chains.
- Interactive Features: Interactive elements such as video players, downloadable resources, and forms for inquiries or newsletter subscriptions.

Integration with Other Platforms

The website will serve as the central node, integrating with other RAASCCEMAN communication and dissemination tools:

- Links to social media platforms (LinkedIn, YouTube) for updates and video content.
- Embedded newsletters for subscription and distribution.
- References to partner websites and collaborations with EU networks and initiatives.

By acting as the digital cornerstone of RAASCCEMAN, the website will ensure a cohesive and impactful online presence, enabling the project to disseminate its results, foster collaboration, and engage effectively with all its stakeholders.

2.4.2 Social Media

RAASCEMAN will actively engage in a social media (SM) strategy to disseminate project updates, share key milestones, and foster connections with both the professional community and the general public. The main aim is to promote RAASCEMAN's achievements, build awareness about Industry 4.0 technologies, and ensure transparent communication with its audience.

For the Professional Community

To engage with industry professionals, researchers, and academics, RAASCEMAN will focus on the following platforms:

- **LinkedIn:** Over the last few years, LinkedIn has become a social media platform for business and employment, popular among audiences who go there to share industry expertise and offer nuanced knowledge. As the primary platform for professional engagement, RAASCEMAN regularly posts updates on the project's progress, share research papers, conference presentations, and industry news related to Industry 4.0, flexible and resilient manufacturing. Regular interaction with followers, partners, and stakeholders will foster a dynamic exchange of ideas and information. LinkedIn will also be used for promoting collaboration opportunities within the professional network and providing insights into the project's technical innovations.
- **Other social media channels:** RAASCEMAN will consider to activate also other social media platforms. Alongside LinkedIn, ResearchGate is a key social media platform for reaching out to industrial and scientific professionals. Researchers, engineers, and scientists widely use it to share publications, collaborate, and discuss industry-related topics. Many industry experts, researchers and executives also share their knowledge, publications and network through X or Mastodon. Rather than through a newly established social network profile, the dissemination will be done through already established institutional or individual profiles of RAASCEMAN's partners and team members.

For the General Public

To raise wider awareness of the RAASCEMAN project among the general public, content will also be disseminated on Facebook through the institutional profiles of the partner organisations to target a wider audience. This will allow RAASCEMAN to leverage the existing online networks of the participating organisations and tap into these already-established channels. As this platform will be used more sparingly, RAASCEMAN will produce posts highlighting project milestones, sharing general knowledge and promoting public activities such as webinars, workshops or events.

LinkedIn communication campaigns and a series of posts will be launched and conducted to raise attention and build the audience whenever appropriate. We build on the initial introduction of project partners and their insights by expanding into key thematic areas. Future posts can cover real-world supply chain challenges (e.g., disruptions due to market changes on both supply and demand sites, geopolitical risks etc.), highlight innovative solutions emerging from the project, and provide behind-the-scenes insights into research and technology development. Engaging formats like expert interviews, case studies, and interactive polls can foster discussion. Additionally, updates on milestones and findings, collaborations with industry stakeholders, and real-world applications of RAASCEMAN's work will help establish thought leadership. By balancing technical depth with accessible storytelling, we aim to engage a broad audience, from policymakers to industry leaders and researchers, fostering a community focused on supply chain resilience.

Examples of social media banners as prepared for initial introductory campaign in RAASCEMAN corporate design:

MEET OUR PARTNERS

CONTINENTAL
AUTOMOTIVE CZ
BRANDÝS N/L, CZECH REPUBLIC

“The motivation of a global player like us is quite clear: supply chain management and complexity of our production process must be managed fully automatically in the future.”

JAKUB HAMERNIK
Head of Smart Automation

www.raasceman.eu

MEET OUR PARTNERS

DFKI
KAISERSLAUTERN, GERMANY

“The capabilities and benefits of the RAASCCEMAN technology will be demonstrated in our network of partner testbeds. This will better explain the use of the technology on both a technical and economic level and facilitate its transfer into real industrial environments.”

ACHIM WAGNER
Coordinator

www.raasceman.eu

Encouraging Engagement with Partners

All project partners will be strongly encouraged to post and share RAASCCEMAN-related content across their social media profiles, both institutional and personal. This collaborative approach will amplify the reach of the project's updates and help integrate RAASCCEMAN within a broader network of professionals, researchers, and stakeholders.

By sharing content, posting comments, and engaging with external networks, partners will help create a multiplier effect, ensuring that the project's key messages reach the right people in the industry, research, and policy circles. A coordinated effort across partner institutions will help foster a sense of collective ownership of the project's success and increase its visibility.

Community YouTube Channel

A key component of RAASCCEMAN's social media strategy will be the creation of a community YouTube channel. This channel will serve as a centralized platform for sharing video content, including:

- Recordings of events: Video recordings from major RAASCCEMAN events, such as workshops and webinars will be uploaded to the channel. These recordings will make RAASCCEMAN's content easily accessible to both the professional community and the general public, ensuring that knowledge sharing is available to anyone interested, regardless of location.
- Training Courses: RAASCCEMAN will share training videos and tutorials related to the project's work, such as tutorials on how to use RAASCCEMAN tools, software, or digital twins. These videos will not only contribute to the education and training goals of the project but also provide a valuable resource for stakeholders looking to implement similar technologies in their work.
- Use-case Videos: Short use-case videos will demonstrate how RAASCCEMAN's solutions can be applied in various industry settings, such as automotive, bicycle manufacturing, and machine tools in real-world settings.

All videos will include links to the project's website for more information and vice-versa, all video content will be accessible through the website and promoted on RAASCCEMAN's social media channels to drive traffic and engagement. This approach of cross-promotion of all online RAASCCEMAN's presence will be applied in general to create a multifaceted approach to engagement and increase the visibility of RAASCCEMAN across multiple digital channels. By engaging with both professional and general audiences through tailored content and strategic outreach, RAASCCEMAN will be able to maintain a strong online presence, ensure that its findings and technologies are widely disseminated, and build a strong online community around the project's activities.

2.4.3 Newsletter

KPI:

2 Newsletters/year

All news and key announcements related to the RAASCCEMAN project will be collected in a branded newsletter tentatively titled "RAASCCEMAN Update" or similar. The newsletter will contain concise, informative content with professional design elements to effectively engage its audience. Its main objective is to establish and maintain regular communication with the RAASCCEMAN community, including industrial partners, academic bodies and research institutions, as well as anyone interested in the progress of the project. The newsletter will be published and distributed on a semi-annual basis. The content of the newsletter will evolve as the project progresses. Initially, it will focus on updates and presentation of more general objectives and approaches, while over time the content will become more focused on specific findings and will also be more sector specific.

Key Content Areas

- **Project Updates and Milestones:** Regular updates on the progress of RAASCCEMAN, including the development of new tools, frameworks, successful pilot demonstrations, or technological innovations.
- **Events and Conferences:** Information on upcoming events, workshops, and conferences where RAASCCEMAN will be presented or will contribute. We will also highlight past events and summarize key takeaways, providing valuable insight for stakeholders incl. links to video content, reports and recordings.
- **Results and Achievements:** A showcase of the most notable research outcomes, including publications, new collaborations, cutting-edge AI-driven manufacturing solutions such as the MaaS platform or product digital twins.
- **Feature Articles:** Non-scientific articles, including interviews with key project members, media outputs or case studies detailing the application of RAASCCEMAN's technologies in real-world manufacturing scenarios.
- **Partnership Opportunities and Services:** As the project matures, the newsletter will feature information on service offerings related to RAASCCEMAN's research infrastructure, along with opportunities for partnerships and collaborations within the network.

From a technical point of view, the newsletter will be first issued in HTML on the RAASCCEMAN website and in its more concise form will be distributed via a mailing application (i.e. Mailchimp) to specific subscribers. The subscription can be done through the website. Participants in workshops will be added to the mailing list based on their consent.

2.4.4 Promotional Materials

RAASCCEMAN will produce several promotional materials to raise awareness of the project among a wide range of stakeholders and to visually and informatively represent the project at events and other public forums. These materials will be designed according to RAASCCEMAN's identity to communicate the consortium, the project objectives and RAASCCEMAN's innovative approach and solutions, ensuring brand consistency across all project-related communications. By utilizing the following materials, RAASCCEMAN will ensure that its key messages are communicated effectively on various occasions to all relevant stakeholders, from industry decision-makers and engineers to researchers, students, and the general public.

Roll-up

One of the primary promotional materials will be the Roll-up banner, which will be used at workshops, and networking events. These visually appealing, portable banners will feature concise, eye-catching graphics, key facts about the project, and QR codes linking to more information on the RAASCCEMAN website.

Flyer

In addition to roll-up, an A5 flyer will be created for distribution at conferences, trade shows, networking events, workshops, partner meetings and public engagement activities. It will provide an overview of the RAASCCEMAN project, including its objectives, major partners, and general information on the RAASCCEMAN use cases. They will be designed to be informative yet concise, offering clear explanations of the project's potential impact on different industries, such as automotive, machine tools, and bicycle manufacturing.

General Slide deck/ Presentation

RAASCCEMAN will also produce slide deck to showcase the project's work in a unified and consistent form by all partners at various occasions and events. More detailed presentations will be used in formal settings such as conferences and industry meetings to explain the technical details of the RAASCCEMAN platform, MaaS framework, and digital tools.

Online Promotional Materials

All physical materials such as a flyer will be complemented with much richer promotional assets that will be available online, such as social media posts, infographics, slideshow etc. These assets will be shared via RAASCCEMAN's official channels and partner networks to increase the project's reach, inform audiences about new developments, and encourage engagement with the project's website and other communication tools.

2.4.5 Non-scientific Articles and Media Input

Press releases, articles and interviews once published on specialised portals and e-magazines at national and EU levels will be displayed in electronic form on the RAASCCEMAN's website and distributed also via an electronic newsletter (NL). Impactful tool for regular updates on RAASCCEMAN's progress and achievements.

RAASCCEMAN will actively issue press releases, articles, and interviews as key tools for communicating the progress, achievements, and breakthroughs of the project. This content will be published in electronic form and distributed through multiple channels to ensure maximum reach and impact.

Press Releases

RAASCCEMAN project press releases will be issued whenever there is a major advance in the project, whether it is the successful testing of a demonstrator or the publication of a major project achievement or finding impacting on key milestones or collaborations. These reports will be produced in coordination with the PR departments of RAASCCEMAN's partner institutions, who will also ensure their widest possible distribution to the media through their established channels. The text will be formulated in a way that is both understandable to the general public and sufficiently interesting for experts in the field with a clear explanation of the impact on industry, economy and sustainability. These press releases will be distributed to mainstream media, including sector-specific publications, and will be available on the official project website as well as on the home institutions and social media channels. The project team will also make use of all distribution opportunities at the European level through the channels provided for the communication of European projects.

Articles

Articles will be written to delve deeper into specific aspects of the RAASCCEMAN project, such as technical innovations, case studies, or future trends in advanced and resilient manufacturing. These articles will aim to educate and inform a specialized audience, offering insights into RAASCCEMAN's cutting-edge solutions, challenges overcome during development, and the broader impact on industries like automotive, bicycle industry, and machinery. Articles will be prepared on-demand for specialized portals and sector-specific magazines. They will also be promoted through newsletters, providing direct links to readers.

Interviews/Podcasts

To personalize and humanize the project, interviews with key project partners, researchers, and industry experts will be featured in collaboration with professional media and platforms. These interviews will focus on individual perspectives regarding RAASCCEMAN's research outcomes, the importance of the project in advancing Industry

4.0 or the environmental implications of resilient supply chains. They will offer a closer look at the human side of the innovation process, emphasizing collaboration and the real-world application of the project’s results.

Distribution and Channels

All of these materials (press releases, articles, and interviews) will be distributed through a multi-channel approach:

- RAASCCEMAN’s official website and social media platforms for direct updates and engagement with followers.
- Specialized industry portals and e-magazines for wider exposure within relevant professional communities.
- Electronic newsletters (NL), sent directly to subscribers, ensuring a targeted distribution of content to stakeholders interested in the project’s developments.
- Collaborations with major EU and national media outlets to reach broader audiences in computer science and Industry 4.0 sectors.

2.5 Phases of the Communication

Communication activities will be implemented in 3 different phases, as can be seen in the figure below. The ultimate goal is to iteratively build an engaged community of stakeholders and end users who are willing to share an open, dedicated space for active interaction, collaboration and feedback. Through clear and transparent communication, RAASCCEMAN aims to demonstrate the benefits it brings to its partners and broader audiences.

By utilizing these channels, RAASCCEMAN will ensure that its achievements and progress are consistently communicated and that stakeholders at all levels stay informed about the project’s outcomes and impacts. These communication activities will serve as an impactful tool for maintaining regular updates and increasing the visibility of RAASCCEMAN’s contributions to the industrial and scientific landscape.

3 Dissemination Strategy

Communication and dissemination are defined as two highly interlinked types of actions, that can be to a certain extent addressed separately though always in close dependence on one another. It is obvious that similarities and convergences exist and those will be carefully examined throughout the whole lifespan of the project. Communication is mainly characterised by promoting the project and its results to reach out to broader audiences. Dissemination conducts actions that drive awareness, use and uptake of project results. Special attention is given to ensuring that the project's results are not only disseminated but also utilized effectively in real-world applications. This includes validating the technical and economic viability of MaaS in two challenging industrial use cases, which serve as a practical demonstration of RAASCCEMAN's innovative solutions.

3.1 Dissemination Assets

The dissemination of RAASCCEMAN's results will focus on tangible outcomes that showcase the project's scientific and industrial achievements. These assets will ensure the project's legacy and impact extend beyond its duration. RAASCCEMAN's open-source results will be shared through industry networks, research publications, and open-access platforms to foster wider adoption and collaboration. Targeted messaging based on the main dissemination assets will highlight how MaaS can enhance supply chain resilience and production adaptability and emphasize how this business model allows companies to switch between suppliers and adapt production processes dynamically.

In general, the main dissemination assets are of the following types:

Scientific Results

- Research Publications: Peer-reviewed papers in high-impact journals, conference proceedings, posters and presentations at relevant conferences to disseminate RAASCCEMAN's findings to the academic and scientific communities.

Datasets and Libraries (aligned with the Data Management Plan)

- Development of open-access datasets and libraries to support reproducibility, encourage collaboration, and facilitate adoption of RAASCCEMAN innovations by researchers and developers.
- Digital twins of production process chain elements within the extended value chain.

Standards and Best Practices

- Contributions to the development of industry standards and guidelines related to the EDC, AAS and OPC-UA interfaces; promoting consistent and scalable implementations.)
- Dissemination of best practices for adopting MaaS models and other innovative approaches developed within the project.

Use-Case Scenarios and Pilots

- Presentation of real-world examples from the automotive and bike industries and pilot lines demonstrate how MaaS and remanufacturing can mitigate the impact of unforeseen events and showcase RAASCCEMAN's solutions in action and their effectiveness in solving practical manufacturing challenges.
- Development of tutorials, training sessions, and demo videos to maximize the adoption of RAASCCEMAN technologies by industry and academia.

Key Applications of RAASCCEMAN Solutions in Industry

- Platform and Framework Deployment: RAASCCEMAN's MaaS framework offers standards, methods, tools, and guidelines for the development of Industry 4.0-compliant platforms, ensuring interoperability across systems.
- Data Models for Product Lifecycle: The Product Digital Twin (PDT) and Digital Product Passport (DPP) data models enable end-to-end lifecycle management, supporting the reuse, repair, and remanufacturing of products in various sectors.

- Decision Support and Planning Tools: Tools for dynamic supply chain generation, scheduling, and execution of manufacturing tasks (including online trajectory planning for robots).

Key Exploitable Assets/ Results (KERs)

RAASCCEMAN’s KERs will be highlighted as the main outputs of the project with the potential for uptake, further research, or integration into existing systems. KERs and their exploitation pathways will be detailed in deliverables on *Exploitation Strategy, IP Management and Business Case* (D6.2-D6.4). With reference to these documents, KERs can be in general segmented according to the following types:

- Software tools and services (and their prototypes)
- Software methodology, proof-of-concept, tool demonstrators.
- Framework and platforms, incl. standards, methods, guidelines.
- Data models and digital twins.
- Pilots – datasets and knowledge/demonstrators.
- Demonstration of new business models built on MaaS.
- Training, educational courses and other forms of knowledge transfer.
- Recommendations for policies in European manufacturing.

3.2 Specification of Target Groups

RAASCCEMAN’s dissemination efforts will be strategically designed to engage a broad spectrum of stakeholders, ensuring the project’s outcomes reach and influence key audiences. RAASCCEMAN will leverage the active participation and position of the consortium in existing relevant ecosystems to create synergies that link collaboration between sectors and key stakeholders. Their already consolidated networks will be an ideal starting point to establish collaborations with other organisations in the main focus areas of the project.

RAASCCEMAN’s stakeholders map for dissemination obviously builds on the target groups as described in the section on communication and deals with their specifics with regard to the potential dissemination of the project results while visually comprising of the following segments:

3.2.1 Industrial Stakeholders and Technology Applications

Industrial stakeholders are essential to RAASCEMAN’s success, particularly in advanced manufacturing and Industry 4.0. They play a key role in implementing, testing, and scaling its solutions, such as MaaS platforms, AI-driven decision support tools, and interoperable data infrastructures. The project aims to equip industries with innovative, scalable solutions that integrate seamlessly into existing processes.

RAASCEMAN’s impact centers on strengthening the manufacturing sector, engaging both SMEs and large corporations as partners in research and implementation. While initial development and validation focus on automotive and bike manufacturing, the results will be immediately applicable across the entire industry, maximizing their significance.

Beyond automotive and bike manufacturing, RAASCEMAN’s tools—covering dynamic supply chain generation, real-time production scheduling, and disruption mitigation—benefit industries such as machinery, aerospace, electronics, food production, and renewable energy. By enhancing supply chain resilience and adaptability, these solutions enable manufacturers to navigate disruptions and fluctuating demands efficiently. The flexibility of RAASCEMAN’s MaaS network makes it invaluable for industries with high complexity, variability, and global supply chains.

Target Businesses and Stakeholders	Description	Specifics
Industrial Manufacturers	These manufacturers are directly impacted by the development and testing of a decentralized MaaS network. RAASCEMAN addresses the challenges of medium- and short-term supply chain disruptions, helping these companies make informed decisions when faced with unforeseen events.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on medium and short-term supply chain challenges. • Involvement in complex and distributed supply chains. • Adoption of new technology such as dynamic production planning and scheduling. • Specific needs in automotive and bike manufacturing, particularly in procurement and adaptability of suppliers. • Automotive: Leveraging RAASCEMAN tools for dynamic supply chain generation and predictive maintenance. • Bike: Using product digital twins for remanufacturing and lifecycle management.
SMEs and Start-ups	Use of scalable and cost-effective tools that drive agility in adopting Industry 4.0 solutions, including digital twins, AI-enabled decision-making, and dynamic production scheduling. These companies often face challenges in sourcing materials from limited suppliers and are vulnerable to disruptions in supply chains.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Struggle with small batch sizes, rush orders, and complex supply chain coordination. • Can benefit from circularity models, utilizing remanufactured goods. • Strong interest in cost-effective solutions to overcome bottlenecks.
System Integrators and Technology Providers	They are key to ensuring that RAASCEMAN’s technology seamlessly integrates into existing manufacturing ecosystems and infrastructures. They are responsible for deploying,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They are responsible for integrating RAASCEMAN’s dynamic scheduling and supply chain management tools with existing systems in factories (e.g., ERP systems, legacy supply chain management tools). • Need to assess the scalability of RAASCEMAN’s solutions in large manufacturing environments and adapt them to different industry contexts.

Target Businesses and Stakeholders	Description	Specifics
	adapting, and maintaining the MaaS solutions across various platforms and industrial environments.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to understand the technical specifications of the tools, particularly the use of advanced algorithms, digital twins, and semantic models for cross-company data exchange. • Key to ensuring the long-term reliability and adaptability of the MaaS network as industry standards and technologies evolve.
Software and Application Developers	Development of customizable software tools and applications based on RAASCCEMAN’s platform and frameworks. These professionals will be responsible for creating and maintaining the software interfaces that users interact with to execute dynamic planning, scheduling, and supply chain management.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They will develop the tools and interfaces required to support RAASCCEMAN’s automated recommendation engine, risk analysis tools, and supply chain monitoring systems. • User experience focus on creating intuitive, user-friendly applications that present complex data in a digestible form for supply chain managers and decision-makers. • Need to integrate the project’s technologies, including digital twins and semantic matching, to ensure smooth and effective communication between manufacturing systems and external suppliers. • Involvement in refining and updating the tools based on user feedback, ensuring that the software is continuously optimized to meet changing industrial needs and challenges.
Supply Chain Managers and Decision Makers	These stakeholders need real-time, actionable data to manage disruptions and ensure supply chain resilience.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highly involved in procurement, dynamic planning, and optimization. • Looking for tools to improve the accuracy of supply chain decisions and shorten the time to identify and manage disruptions. • Need information on how to effectively use new technologies such as Bayesian inference networks and semantic matching.

RAASCCEMAN will engage with this ecosystem to obtain hands-on requirements and feedback that will support the implementation of the project and its application cases, understand internal processes, system integration and risk management, access quality data acquisition, raise wide-range awareness and trust on the positive impact MaaS concept and network will have in complex real-world scenarios.

- **Purpose & Aim:** To provide tailored solutions for enhancing resilience, digitalization, and automation in manufacturing.
- **Key Needs:** Information about how the RAASCCEMAN tools can help mitigate supply chain disruptions, improve production adaptability, and enhance circular economy practices.
- **Relevant Information:** Information about how RAASCCEMAN's tools for increasing their competitiveness, such as dynamic production planning, remanufacturing, and MaaS, can enhance adaptability, reduce operational costs, and support supply chain resilience in response to unforeseen events.
- **Focus Areas:** Automotive, machinery, and other manufacturing sectors, with an emphasis on SMEs seeking cost-effective, innovative solutions.

A consolidated overview of industrial stakeholders is also described in *D1.1 Requirements and Specifications*, chapter 3.4.3, which operates with a categorisation of stakeholders into Manufacturing service requester, Manufacturing service provider and MaaS network provider.

3.2.2 Academic and Research Communities

Research bodies and experts with interest in the development of MaaS networks and their application to real-world industrial challenges. RAASCCEMAN actively engages with the academic and research communities to drive further advancements in AI, robotics, and automation technologies. By fostering collaborations with universities and research institutions, RAASCCEMAN ensures the continuous evolution of the technology through scientific validation, prototyping, and feedback loops.

Target Research Stakeholders

- Universities and Research Institutions: Focus on ICT, AI, robotics, and manufacturing automation.
- PhD and Early-Stage Researchers: Opportunities for involvement in advanced AI/robotics projects, as well as the development of innovative solutions for Industry 4.0.
- Collaborative Research Networks: RAASCCEMAN partners with prominent AI initiatives such as AI4EU and DIHs to facilitate knowledge sharing and adoption of cutting-edge research in industrial applications.

Specifics:

- Interested in evaluating and testing RAASCCEMAN technologies in terms of innovation, scalability, and technical viability.
- Focus on the application of advanced algorithms like model predictive control and dynamic supply chain generation.
- Engagement in validating the technical and economic viability of MaaS.

Research Dissemination Channels

- Scientific publications and conferences dedicated to advanced manufacturing and Industry 4.0.
- Workshops and collaborative projects with EU-funded research networks.
- Integration of RAASCCEMAN's innovations into ongoing research in AI, machine learning, and smart manufacturing.

Scientific collaboration on the practical applications of MaaS, digital twins, and circular economy practices in real-world manufacturing scenarios is central to the RAASCCEMAN project's success. Academia, research institutions, and early-stage researchers will play a key role in validating project outcomes, refining AI-driven technologies, and integrating these innovations into industry. RAASCCEMAN could serve as a case study or collaboration opportunity for advanced research.

- **Purpose & Aim:** To foster cross-sectoral research and scientific development that directly impacts manufacturing resilience.
- **Relevant Information:** Research outcomes in industrial AI, industrial and process data automation, and quality monitoring in manufacturing, as well as findings from the project's pilot implementations.
- **Engagement:** RAASCCEMAN will:
 - Involve research institutions and universities in knowledge exchange within current and prospective collaborative projects and events.
 - Disseminate research outcomes via academic journals, conferences, and industry events.
 - Engage students and early-stage researchers in hands-on research, internships, and project-based learning opportunities.

3.2.3 Students as a Specific Target Group

Engaging university students, particularly those in technical fields like engineering, computer science, industrial design, and supply chain management, can be highly beneficial for both the project and the academic community. Relevant departments include industrial engineering, mechanical engineering, robotics, AI, data science, software engineering, logistics and operations management, innovation management, entrepreneurship as well as environmental engineering and management. By targeting students, RAASCCEMAN

not only helps bridge the gap between academia and industry but also fosters a future workforce skilled in the latest technologies, which can be pivotal in driving the innovation of tomorrow's manufacturing industries.

- **Educational outreach:** RAASCCEMAN can share its research outcomes and innovations through educational materials such as webinars, guest lectures, and workshops. These activities can be conducted at universities and research institutions, aiming to increase awareness of the project's technologies and their real-world applications in areas like AI, manufacturing, and supply chain resilience.
- **Collaborative research and internships:** RAASCCEMAN could offer students opportunities for internships, research projects, or collaboration on case studies related to its use cases, such as automotive, bike manufacturing, and interconnected pilot lines. This can provide students with hands-on experience working with advanced AI tools and manufacturing processes and expose them to cutting-edge industry challenges.
- **Knowledge sharing and mentorship:** Engaging students through mentorship programs or by inviting them to participate in RAASCCEMAN's workshops, hackathons, or innovation challenges would not only provide them with exposure to the project's technologies but also encourage them to explore the real-world applications of AI in manufacturing and supply chain management.

3.2.4 Synergies with EU and National Networks

RAASCCEMAN will strengthen its presence and impact by collaborating with established EU and national research initiatives, innovation hubs, and manufacturing networks. These collaborations will help integrate RAASCCEMAN's results into broader research and industry ecosystems.

Key Networks and Initiatives

- **AI-based European networks and initiatives:** Collaboration with AI and robotics initiatives such as European associations and innovation platforms, ADRA and ADRA-e ecosystems, Gaia-X, ELLIS, CAIRNE, EFFRA, IDSA and their ecosystems to ensure RAASCCEMAN's alignment with leading-edge research and development.
- **European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs):** Involvement of some of the RAASCCEMAN's partners in (E)DIHs can facilitate the integration of new technologies into industrial practice and accelerate the adoption of some of the RAASCCEMAN solutions. EDIHs serve as one-stop-shops for industries that offer digital services, consultancy, education, training and networking for companies. As they collaborate with each other, EDIHs assist in coupling with counterparts across the EU.
- **Industry networks and professional communities:** RAASCCEMAN will partner with manufacturing-focused networks, such as EIT Manufacturing and euRobotics, to further expand its technology reach and ensure alignment with industry standards and best practices.
- **Organizations such as the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) and sector-specific consortia that drive the standardization of manufacturing and supply chain technologies.**
- **EU-Funded Projects and European Networks of AI Centers of Excellence (NoEs):** Engagement with European NoEs currently under implementation (dAIEDGE, ELIAS, ELSA, ENFIELD, euROBIN) and related projects such as AI4Europe to strengthen the academic reach of RAASCCEMAN's results and leveraging the collaboration among Europe's leading experts and centres.

Industrial Associations like *EFFRA* (European Factory of the Future Research Association), *AIOTI* (Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation), and *DAIRO* (Digital Automated Industry Research Organisation) play a crucial role in the industrial ecosystem. They serve as important intermediaries between research, technology development, and industrial practices. They work on advancing the industrial sector through collaborative research, technology dissemination, and policy advocacy. These associations often bring together manufacturers, suppliers, research organizations, and policymakers to promote the adoption of new technologies, best practices, and standardization across industries.

Given that RAASCCEMAN is focused on creating resilient supply chains and adapting production networks through MaaS technologies, engaging with these associations is key for:

- Raising awareness about RAASCCEMAN's solutions.
- Fostering collaboration and partnerships with various stakeholders.
- Guiding industrial decision-makers toward the adoption of RAASCCEMAN's tools.

These associations play a strategic advisory role, influence the direction of research and innovation within European industries, and can help connect RAASCCEMAN with the right stakeholders across the manufacturing ecosystem.

3.2.5 Policy Makers & Regulators

European Commission representatives, national governments, industry regulators (such as IDTA - Industrial Digital Twin Association) and other stakeholders in policy-making or regulations responsible for shaping policies on manufacturing, supply chain resilience, digital transformation, and circular economy initiatives. RAASCCEMAN's findings can inform policy recommendations, ensuring alignment with European values and industry standards. Policy development is key to ensuring that the outcomes of RAASCCEMAN align with EU and national strategies for industrial modernization. By engaging policymakers and professional associations, RAASCCEMAN can influence policy decisions that support the adoption of Industry 4.0 solutions.

Specifics:

- Interest in how RAASCCEMAN contributes to European supply chain resilience.
- Concern with sustainability goals, particularly circularity and the reduction of supply chain dependencies on external geopolitical risks.
- Focus on supporting projects aligned with Europe's climate neutrality goals by 2050.
- **Purpose & Aim:** To engage with policymakers and industry associations to shape policies that support digital transformation in manufacturing.
- **Relevant Information:** Policy briefs, research outcomes, and evidence-based recommendations regarding the implementation of AI and digital technologies in manufacturing.
- **Engagement:** RAASCCEMAN will:
 - Work with national and EU-level policymakers to align project outcomes with strategic goals for digital transformation.
 - Participate in or support industry-wide discussions through platforms like ADRA, Gaia-X, and EIT Manufacturing.
 - Provide insights on the role of AI in industrial modernization and the social implications of these technological shifts.

3.2.6 Society and Citizen Communities

By educating the public about RAASCCEMAN's work, its technological innovations, and the potential benefits for the European economy and society, the project can also contribute to broader social acceptance of AI and Industry 4.0 technologies. By targeting society and the general public with outreach activities, RAASCCEMAN can foster broader understanding, trust, and support for its technology, while also empowering future generations to participate in Europe's digital transformation and sustainability goals.

- **Purpose & Aim:** Foster public engagement and increase awareness, public acceptance, and understanding of the project's goals and its wider impact.
- **Relevant Information:** Benefits of AI and Industry 4.0 technologies in enhancing manufacturing resilience, as well as insights into their broader societal implications.
- **Expected outcomes:**
 - **Public Understanding and Support:** Increased understanding among the general public of RAASCCEMAN's role in building resilient supply chains, which is critical for European economic stability and sustainability.
 - **Increased Trust in Technology:** Public outreach helps build trust in AI, automation, and Industry 4.0 technologies by demonstrating their real-world benefits for industries, workers, and the environment.

- Community Involvement: Encouraging broader societal engagement, particularly through educational initiatives and interactive public events, helps ensure wider acceptance and integration of RAASCEMAN’s innovations.

3.3 Scientific Publications

KPIs:	<p style="color: #004a7c; margin: 0;">7 Journal papers</p> <p style="color: #004a7c; margin: 0;">15 conference papers</p>
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The scientific community will be addressed through research papers on the advancements in supply chain resilience, dynamic scheduling, and MaaS in peer-reviewed journals (Elsevier, SpringerOpen - Robotics & Artificial Intelligence; IJAIR; Frontiers in Robotics and AI, various IEEE Transactions etc.). The results will be presented at major industry, academic and high-impact international conferences (IFAC, ECAI, IEEE - ICRA, IROS, IEEE SMC, AAAI, EURAMAS, AAMAS) to reach a global audience of researchers and technology developers. The results will be presented in open access either in journals/book or by such tools as Open Research Europe and Zenodo repository.

- 25+ high-level scientific publications and conference presentations,
- At least 5 open access publications with the most renown publishers

3.3.1 Zenodo Community

Zenodo is an open-access platform that supports the storage and sharing of various types of scientific content, allowing researchers to make their work widely available while ensuring proper attribution and visibility. Scientific dissemination through Zenodo involves uploading and sharing research outputs, such as publications, datasets, presentations, and other academic materials, in a publicly accessible and citable manner. By assigning a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to each submission, Zenodo enhances the discoverability of research and ensures that contributors receive recognition for their work. It serves as a valuable tool for scientific communities, enabling seamless dissemination and fostering collaboration across disciplines.

For RAASCEMAN, it offers an efficient way to share results, reports, and datasets with the broader scientific community, including stakeholders, researchers, and policy makers. The RAASCEMAN’s profile has been created and will be used by all team members continuously.

<https://zenodo.org/communities/raasceman/>

3.3.2 AI-on-Demand Platform

To reach out to innovation and scientific communities, RAASCEMAN will be also present at the AI-on-Demand platform that serves for sharing research findings, tools, and resources related to artificial intelligence (AI) in a collaborative and accessible online environment. The platform is designed to connect researchers, developers, and industry practitioners, allowing them to access AI solutions and research outputs on-demand. For RAASCEMAN, dissemination through this platform can include uploading technical papers, case studies, AI models, software tools, and findings from pilot use cases. By providing access to these resources, the platform

helps to engage a wider audience, including researchers, engineers, and businesses, facilitating the adoption and application of the AI solutions developed. Additionally, the platform can host collaborative spaces for discussions, feedback, and real-time updates, fostering a community-driven approach to innovation. This makes it an ideal channel for sharing the project’s technical advancements and real-world applications while contributing to the broader AI ecosystem.

3.3.3 Scientific Dissemination through Social Media

To maximize the impact of our scientific publications, we will actively disseminate them within larger community through various online platforms. Each new high-level publication, once publicly available, will be introduced on RAASCEMAN LinkedIn profile with a brief summary of the topic/abstract, including the full title, authors, publication year, journal, DOI, key findings as well as a direct link to the full text on journal’s website. Posts will be accompanied by engaging visual content in a unified format and design to help with the visibility of the post and audience engagement. Relevant unifying hashtags such as #RAASCEMANPublications, #RAASCEMANResearch, #RAASCEMANScience will be added and field-specific tags for each of the publications like #Robotics, #SupplyChain, #Industry40 will be used to reach out to a broader industry audience.

New publications will be also highlighted in RAASCEMAN’s newsletter to introduce the topic to all those who are actively interested in the project. To provide long-term visibility and accessibility, all publications will be systematically listed on RAASCEMAN website in a dedicated Results section. Each entry will include the full title, list of authors, publication journal/conference and publication year. To make it easy for visitors to access the full papers, each publication will have a direct link to the journal’s website or open-access repository whenever available.

3.4 Dissemination Activities and Events

Dissemination activities reaching primarily the professional community to support by publication in scientific journals, thematic editions reaching out to the community, complex presentation of demonstrators and open pilots in close collaboration with WP5 for online and onsite dissemination, participation in main conferences and summits, participation in challenges and third-party events etc..

3.4.1 Participation at Third-party events: Liaisons with Innovation Ecosystems

KPIs:	<p style="color: #008080; margin: 0;">6 invited speeches</p> <p style="color: #008080; margin: 0;">10 events attended</p>
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RAASCEMAN can leverage established professional communities of ADRA, EIT Manufacturing, EDIHs, TEF for Manufacturing etc. to spread its research and innovations, engaging in cross-collaborations and knowledge-sharing platforms. The coordinated activities will bring multiple opportunities for dissemination in terms of contributions to their relevant events (preparation of demonstrations as part of their exhibitions, specialised workshops and training for the community members as well as external target audiences and innovation ecosystems, community workshops, convergence summit etc.). Participating in these events and professional summits will be an effective way for outreach to the professional community.

The key European scientific and industrial ecosystems to target include:

ADRA and Adra-e Ecosystems:

- As for the scientific dissemination, the ecosystems of ADRA and ADRA-e is clearly considered as the multiplier for effective dissemination towards key scientific and industrial stakeholders with links to the growing European Innovation ecosystem.
- We will also leverage ADRA-e for supporting the development of such standards maintaining European technological sovereignty.

- Anticipated actions to be considered:
 - Collaborate with ADRA and ADRA-e during the main community events (such as ADRForum, European Convergence Summit, seminars, professional exhibitions, meetings of topic groups and roundtable discussions) to use any relevant opportunity to demonstrate the technological innovations and results from RAASCCEMAN, focusing on how MaaS solutions can improve supply chain resilience.
 - Share RAASCCEMAN's technical papers, whitepapers, and best practices with ADRA and ADRA-e members to encourage further research collaborations.
 - Contribute to community-driven documents such as scientific research agendas and whitepapers on selected topics of common interest like AI-driven supply chain optimization and disruption resilience in manufacturing.

AI-based Initiatives CAIRNE and ELLIS:

- Synergies will be leveraged in close collaboration with the main communities across Europe such as AI-based initiatives CAIRNE and ELLIS. Thanks to the active participation and membership of several RAASCCEMAN's team members in these communities, synergies can be created in terms of common actions, events or other activities.
- Anticipated actions to be considered:
 - Participate in CAIRNE and ELLIS community workshops and conferences, where RAASCCEMAN can present its AI models and the impact of Bayesian inference networks in predicting supply chain disruptions.
 - Organize joint webinars or scientific sessions within these networks to introduce RAASCCEMAN's tools for dynamic production planning and AI-powered decision support systems.
 - Collaborate on AI innovation agendas to include RAASCCEMAN's research on the potential for AI-powered MaaS solutions to enable resilient manufacturing systems.

European Networks of AI Centers of Excellence (NoEs):

- These networks - ELSA, euRobin, ELIAS, dAIEDGE, and ENFIELD - provide a platform for collaboration among Europe's leading AI centers of excellence, aiming to push the boundaries of AI in industrial and societal contexts.
- Anticipated actions to be considered:
 - Participate in joint research knowledge-sharing sessions, contributing RAASCCEMAN's expertise on AI-based supply chain prediction and circular economy practices.
 - Present RAASCCEMAN at AI conferences and innovation workshops hosted by these networks to showcase the impact of AI on industrial resilience.
 - Using the common distribution channels and electronic newsletters of these networks to inform expert audiences about RAASCCEMAN's approach, solutions and events.

EDIH and TEF Networks:

- Several of the RAASCCEMAN partners (LMS, FM, DFKI, CEA and CTU) are also involved in particular (E)DIHs at local and regional levels, CEA and CTU are also involved in AI TEF (Testing and Experimentation Facilities Network) for European industries for Manufacturing - AI-MATTERS (CEA as coordinator, CTU as Czech node leader), and CTU is also seat of EIT Manufacturing Hub Czechia. This intensive and direct involvement of RAASCCEMAN partners in all of these schemes and networks presents a unique opportunity for reaching key industrial stakeholders at the local and regional levels.
- Anticipated actions to be considered:
 - Collaborate on local workshops, demonstrations, and hands-on training events showcasing RAASCCEMAN's MaaS solutions for supply chain resilience.
 - Partner with these entities to create knowledge-sharing platforms focused on the use of RAASCCEMAN's technology.

- Organize community workshops within the EDIH network to help small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) understand and adopt dynamic supply chain generation tools and AI-driven production scheduling.

Sister EU-projects from the call:

- RAASCEMAN will investigate synergies to collaborate more closely with the Horizon Europe funded projects under the same topic HORIZON-CL4-2023-TWIN-TRANSITION-01-07 that implements the co-programmed European Partnership “Made in Europe”. The following 8 projects have been funded:
 - DMaaST - Innovative modelling and assessment capabilities through MaaS for Manufacturing Ecosystem resiliency
 - MAASive – Manufacturing as a service to increase resilience in value networks
 - M4ESTRO - Industrial Manufacturing As a sErvice STRategies and models for flexible, resilient, and reconfigurable value networks through Trusted and Transparent Operations.
 - ACCURATE – Achieving resilience through Manufacturing as a service, digital twins and ecosystems
 - MaaSiveTwin – MAnufacturing as a service And Supply chain predictIve Twin for critical raw materials
 - NARRATE - RegeNerAtive Resilient smaRt mAnufacTuring nEtworks
 - Tec4MaaSes - Technologies for Manufacturing as a Service Ecosystems
- The "**Made in Europe**" Partnership, facilitated by the *European Factories of the Future Research Association (EFFRA)*, is a strategic initiative under the Horizon Europe framework. Its primary goal is to drive sustainable manufacturing in Europe by uniting expertise and resources, thereby enhancing the global competitiveness of European manufacturing ecosystems. The partnership focuses on promoting technological leadership, circular industries, and flexibility within the sector. EFFRA organizes a variety of events to support the objectives of the "Made in Europe" Partnership and RAASCEMAN will investigate options and opportunities in actively participating in the following events to disseminate its outcomes, increase visibility and engage with key manufacturing stakeholders:
 - **Workshops and Consultations:** These events engage stakeholders from industry, academia, and policy-making to discuss and shape the strategic research and innovation agenda. For instance, public consultations have been launched to gather input on draft call topics for upcoming work programs.
 - **Matchmaking Events:** Designed to foster collaboration, these events help participants find potential consortium partners for Horizon Europe projects. EFFRA provides online matchmaking opportunities through the EFFRA Innovation Portal.
 - **Dissemination Workshops and Conferences:** These events focus on sharing project results, best practices, and technological advancements, targeting professionals in manufacturing, research institutions, and policy-makers

Industry Events and Other Innovation Ecosystems:

Through its partners, RAASCEMAN will use opportunities to contribute to key industry events and trade shows such as Hannover Messe, Smart Manufacturing Week, Industry 4.0 conferences and open days at national and regional levels, exhibitions, and specialized workshops for demonstrating the technology's value.

3.4.2 RAASCEMAN Project Events & Hybrid Workshops

KPIs:	<p style="text-align: right; margin: 0;">4 project events</p> <p style="text-align: right; margin: 0;">3 use-case-specific hybrid workshops</p> <p style="text-align: right; margin: 0;">300 participants</p>
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Main RAASCCEMAN events will be organised in the second half of the project, preferably collocated or as a part of selected stakeholders' events such as Industry 4.0 Open Day and others. Specific RAASCCEMAN workshops and tutorials will showcase the project's innovative approach, results and technologies as well as help to engage with stakeholders in the field. Specific user training and hands-on guidance will be also delivered in form of hybrid workshops focusing on the presentation of use-cases for SMEs. By combining scientific events with industry-focused workshops, RAASCCEMAN can ensure that its results are effectively disseminated and adopted across the European manufacturing sector.

Anticipated Concept of the RAASCCEMAN Project Events (to be adapted to the needs, audiences and situation):

Focus:

- Present RAASCCEMAN's innovative technologies and their potential to enhance the resilience of European supply chains, with a special focus on AI-driven tools and dynamic supply chain optimization.
- Demonstrating how RAASCCEMAN's innovations can be scaled and integrated into European industry, focusing on MaaS solutions for medium-term and short-term disruptions.

Proposed Topics:

- Overview of RAASCCEMAN's approach to resilience and agility in manufacturing
- Role of AI, machine learning, and semantic matching in supply chain disruptions
- Case studies from RAASCCEMAN's use cases in automotive and bike manufacturing
- Best practices and lessons learned from the pilot implementations
- Scalability and commercial viability of RAASCCEMAN's MaaS solutions
- How RAASCCEMAN's approach supports the EU's digital transformation strategy for manufacturing
- Lessons from real-world applications in automotive and bike industries
- Insights into AI-powered tools, smart manufacturing, and circularity
- Identifying market opportunities and commercialization pathways for RAASCCEMAN technologies

Format: Half-day summit, workshop with keynote speakers, panel discussions, scientific presentations, networking session and live interactive demonstrations by RAASCCEMAN partners. The event should also have interactive sessions to encourage cross-sector dialogue. Guided tours in testbeds during break or at the end of the event. Such an event can be collocated within larger events such as Industry 4.0 Open Day etc. Onsite venue, eventually also a hybrid format to reach a wider audience.

Examples of thematic focus/title of the events:

Advancing Resilience in European Manufacturing: The Role of AI and Dynamic Supply Chain Management
From Research to Market: Scaling MaaS Innovations for Industry 4.0

Anticipated Concept of the RAASCCEMAN Hybrid Pilot Use Cases Workshops (to be adapted to the needs, audiences and situation):

1. **Workshop on the Automotive Industry Use Case**
2. **Workshop on the Bike Industry Use Case**
3. **Workshop on the Interconnected Pilot Lines Use Case**

Format:

- Hybrid format (in-person & online), half-day
- Introduction to RAASCCEMAN: Overview of the project and the specific pilot use cases.
- Case Study presentation with real-life implementation of RAASCCEMAN's tools in automotive/bike manufacturing, addressing challenges.
- Hands-on training on RAASCCEMAN tools and solutions with alternative scenarios and strategies.
- Practical sessions with group discussions and scenario-based problem-solving.
- Interactive simulations and demonstrations with opportunity to work directly with the software tools and systems.

- Outcomes: Participants will understand how to optimize production processes in a small-batch manufacturing environment and enhance resilience against market fluctuations or how to manage supply chain disruptions, enhance agility and adapt production schedules quickly.
- For each event and workshop, RAASCCEMAN can create digital toolkits and guidelines that summarize the key lessons, technologies, and approaches covered. These can be shared with attendees, posted on RAASCCEMAN's website, and distributed through relevant networks.
- Recordings of the events will be shared through YouTube and will create playlist of guidance video material. After the workshops, RAASCCEMAN will share online resources and follow-up sessions with participants and wider audience for continued engagement, offering participants the opportunity to ask questions, share feedback, and receive additional training or consultation as needed.

3.5 Presentation of Use Cases: Online Information Packages

KPIs:	3 presentation packages 300 views
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RAASCCEMAN's solutions across the three pilot use cases (automotive, bike, and interconnected pilot lines) will be presented through online tailored information packages, which will include multiple communication elements and formats, namely explanatory videos, slide decks, social media campaigns based on user stories. These communication elements will be designed to effectively engage key stakeholders and promote RAASCCEMAN's value proposition. These presentation packages will be shared online on the RAASCCEMAN website, social media channels, and will be also used during the above described RAASCCEMAN's events and workshops.

3.5.1 Slide Deck

Well-designed slide decks and infographics are powerful engagement tools to share the project's vision and scope with specialised audiences in a clear, straightforward and visually attractive way. A slide deck designed for industrial stakeholders, summarizing RAASCCEMAN's solutions and key insights. This deck will be available for download on the website and shared in industry webinars.

Key features:

- Problem Statement: Challenges in the automotive supply chain, such as material shortages and production delays.
- RAASCCEMAN's Solution: Highlighting the AI-driven tools for dynamic scheduling, alternative supplier recommendations, and impact prediction.
- Case Study: Specific results from the automotive pilot use case demonstrating improvements in resilience and cost savings.
- Conclusion: Invitation for collaboration, along with contact information for follow-up inquiries.

3.5.2 Short Videos

Three short videos will explain key aspects of the particular pilot use cases and make them more understandable for a broader audience. It will provide an overview of the RAASCCEMAN solution and feature real-world applications showcasing how RAASCCEMAN's tools enhance.

Dependent on the resources available and offerings, all videos will be a combination of infographics, animation and real footage with shooting from real operations and with live speakers/RAASCCEMAN representatives.

Key features:

- Introduction to automotive/ bike/ interconnected pilot lines use cases
- Challenge and scenario visualisation
- RAASCCEMAN approach & Resulted solution

- Final slide – QR-Code to website, obligatory publicity, partners

3.5.3 Social Media Campaign & User Stories

A multi-post campaign aims to generate engagement and awareness within the particular industries. The campaigns will use short-form content, including snippets from the videos, infographics, and key facts.

Key features:

- Teaser Post/Challenge: "Is your supply chain prepared for the next disruption? Discover how RAASCEMAN can help."
- Video Post: A short, attention-grabbing clip from the video or infographic/visual showing how RAASCEMAN's tools mitigate supply chain risks in automotive/bike manufacturing.
- User story & Testimonial: A quote or case example from RAASCEMAN's pilot use case, highlighting tangible results, made by RAASCEMAN industrial representative and/or other users.
- RAASCEMAN Solution/Result: Outline the RAASCEMAN's approach and method supported with the impact for the company (can be supported with a quotation of the RAASCEMAN scientific team member).
- Call to Action: "Find out how RAASCEMAN can enhance your production resilience."

3.6 Horizon Results Platform and the Innovation Radar

The Horizon Results Platform and the Innovation Radar offer a structured environment for sharing project results with key stakeholders and are excellent channels for enhancing visibility for RAASCEMAN's outcomes, ensuring that the project's results are communicated to a broad range of stakeholders, from industrial manufacturers, policy makers, investors, technology providers and business leaders to the general public. These platforms focus on showcasing the impact of EU-funded research projects, fostering collaboration, and enabling the uptake of innovative solutions in the market.

The **Horizon Results Platform** is an EU initiative designed to help projects funded under Horizon Europe (and its predecessor programs) share their results, making them accessible to a wide range of stakeholders and ensuring the impact of EU funding is maximized. RAASCEMAN can use this platform as follows:

- Showcase innovation and results: The platform allows RAASCEMAN to publish detailed information about its technological innovations, scientific breakthroughs, and pilot outcomes, including the tools developed for dynamic supply chain generation, AI-powered recommendations for suppliers, and resilience-building capabilities.
- Engage with EU Networks: The Horizon Results Platform facilitates connections between EU-funded projects and various European innovation networks, including industry leaders, research organizations, and clusters.
- Use Success Stories: RAASCEMAN can showcase success stories from its industrial use cases (e.g., in automotive and bike manufacturing) to demonstrate the real-world impact of its solutions. Highlighting these successful demonstrations can increase confidence among potential users, partners, and investors, enhancing the project's visibility in relevant sectors.
- Link to Future Funding Opportunities: RAASCEMAN can also explore further funding opportunities through the platform, as the platform often provides information on upcoming calls, opportunities for commercialization, and new R&D projects where their results can be integrated or scaled up.

The **Innovation Radar** is a European Commission tool that identifies and highlights high-potential innovations emerging from EU-funded research projects. It aims to help these innovations reach the market, gain visibility, and attract investors. RAASCEMAN can leverage the Innovation Radar as follows:

- Highlight High-Impact Innovations: RAASCEMAN can feature its key innovations (e.g., AI-driven dynamic supply chain management tools, resilience analysis tools, automated supplier recommendations) in the Innovation Radar. These innovations can be categorized and promoted according to their market readiness, scientific value, and technological impact.

- **Attract Investment and Partnerships:** By showcasing its innovations, RAASCEMAN can attract investment opportunities and partnerships from industry players, venture capitalists, and technology providers interested in scaling these solutions. This can be especially important in building sustainable business models or launching spin-off companies based on RAASCEMAN's technologies.
- **Increased Market Uptake:** The Innovation Radar promotes innovations that have the potential to be commercialized. By being listed on this platform, RAASCEMAN can gain credibility and increase its chances of market uptake, helping the technologies gain traction among industrial sectors across Europe and beyond.
- **Public Recognition and Visibility:** The Innovation Radar is regularly used by the European Commission, research networks, and innovation stakeholders as a go-to resource for discovering breakthrough innovations. RAASCEMAN's presence on the platform enhances its reputation within the EU innovation ecosystem and shows its alignment with Europe's goals of digital transformation and supply chain resilience.

Both platforms provide exposure to a wide audience across Europe and globally, facilitating networking, collaboration, and commercialization. Listing on these platforms positions RAASCEMAN's innovations as credible and market-ready, increasing confidence among industry stakeholders and policy makers. Both platforms serve as a springboard for attracting investments and new funding opportunities, vital for scaling and further development of RAASCEMAN's solutions. By showcasing the impact of RAASCEMAN's solutions on industrial resilience, these platforms will help measure the societal and economic benefits of the project, increasing its visibility among broader audiences.

4 Reference to the Exploitation Strategy

Within WP6, together with the dissemination, promotion and communication-based activities, as well as standardisation efforts, the exploitation and IPR team work in tandem to maximize the impact of the RAASCEMAN project during and after its contractual lifetime.

Essentially, dissemination is „during“ the project, and exploitation takes over „after“ the contractual end of the project, but our potential targets, stakeholder groups and main reach-out channels of promotion are essentially very similar.

4.1 Action Alignment

4.1.1 Promotion of exploitable assets

We both select and promote assets in terms

- Maturity / Innovativeness /wide applicability.
- impact to society challenges.
- potential to influence policy making.
- ability to instigate strong collaboration with wider ecosystems and research initiatives, adoption potential by market leader in key sector of the economy.
- having a clear “route to market” potential as per Innovation Radar terms.

4.1.2 Extend the Value Proposition

Already, T6.1 has derived a preliminary „Value Proposition“ for communication purposes. It is considered sufficient for now (M6), but it will be further expanded by the exploitation team into full VPC (Value Proposition Canvases) and BMC (Business Model Canvases) in the next exploitation stages (M18 & M36).

It stands as follows (for the project). After the exploitation plans are in a first mature version (after M18), we shall derive Value propositions in a more granular way: Per asset per partner and per exploitation plan proposed (rather than one for the whole project):

- developing and testing a decentralized capability-based MaaS network creating resilience for European supply chains while enabling the human to make informed decisions in case of medium- and short-term disruptions.
- transforming supply chain resilience through innovative, decentralized solutions. By leveraging Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS) networks, digital twins, and circularity-driven practices, RAASCEMAN empowers manufacturers to swiftly adapt to unforeseen disruptions, ensuring continuity and efficiency.

4.1.3 Extend Targets

As an exploitation overall methodology, we distinguish between Customers (paid or for free), wider adopters and beneficiaries overall (more on the subject after the first exploitation workshop and relevant online survey in the M18 deliverable). An example is below:

<input type="checkbox"/> Customer who would potentially pay	<input type="checkbox"/> Adopter Governmental - Policy maker - Standardisation Body
<input type="checkbox"/> Customer for free (example opensource)	<input type="checkbox"/> Adopter (trial user to evaluate us)
<input type="checkbox"/> Adopter of our Usecase-Pilot who would repeat-expand the pilot in their premises	<input type="checkbox"/> Internal customer (within our organisation)
<input type="checkbox"/> Adopter of Research idea	

We aspire (in collaboration of all WP6 Tasks together during our common efforts to reach the following targets):

- Alignment and Expansion of Stakeholders, from communication liaisons towards potential exploitation targets, customers and adopters after the end of the project.
- These lists which are constantly updated, currently include the following categories which we would like to consider expanding (if applicable) for exploitation purposes: Target Businesses and Stakeholders, Industrial Manufacturers, SMEs and Start-ups, System Integrators and Technology Providers, Software and Application Developers, Supply Chain Managers and Decision Makers
- We wish to engage the partners’ pre-existing network of friends, collaborators, vendors, suppliers, common research partners, etc. Into a first list of potential targets for adoption (after the contractual end of the project)
- We aspire to gather up to 50-100 Organizations from the Real Market, and to develop at least 5 common market offerings (based on 4-5 exploitation plans that our partners will formulate later in the project) all together shaped as a showcase. (during our last big exploitation workshop in M36).

4.2 IPR Time-Plan & Phases

As technical work progresses, our IPR strategy will deepen with more granularity gradually. In line with the deliverable iterations (see plan in chapter 4.3) we expect to:

- **M6 PHASE 1:** Deploy the knowledge registry, set the IPR methods, and devise the preliminary tables.
- **M12 PHASE 2:** Formulate the IPR claims tables (Background-Foreground-Contribution Levels).
- **M18 PHASE 3:** Derive Intention to Exploit/License/Open Potential
- **M24 PHASE 4:** Expand into the official IPRMATRIX[®] and the IPR Helpdesk proposed Tables in their „mini“ condensed versions. Revise Registry if needed
- **M30 PHASE 5:** Address subjects of Licensing, Protection Instruments and Restriction Measures.
- **M36 PHASE 6:** Address subjects of Availability (for Assets and for Documentation of Assets) and sustainability after the project closure.

We are in-line with the IPR phases proposed by IPR Helpdesk:

4.3 Exploitation Time-plan of Actions – Relation to Deliverable Iterations

The above-mentioned tools and action points will be broken down within deliverable iterations (i.e. periodical report of D6.2, v1 on M6, v2 on M18, and v3 on M36 respectively), through exploitation workshop revisions, and in parallel with online surveys on the business plans and marketing plans, by using the 44 checklist points as a guideline, according to the following schema.

5 Monitoring and KPIs

KPIs
Corporate identity and toolbox
Website
Media input, non-scientific articles and interviews
Electronic Newsletter
Social media appearance (LinkedIn)
Scientific publications
Participating in conferences, professional summits and workshops
Project events and Hybrid workshops on use cases (incl. specific training)
Presentation of use-cases & demos – online info package, video, slide deck, campaign

KPIs measurement matrix for monitoring, updating, and evaluation of the communication and dissemination actions has been proposed in the following structure that will serve as basis for creating a shared table **C&D Tracker** for collecting and monitoring of all relevant activities:

Date	Type of the activity*	Title of the activity	Partner lead / involved	Outreach** (preferably according to target groups, if feasible)						Relevant html links
				Total	Academia	Industry	General Public	Policy Makers	Media	

Types of activities:

Events: Organisation of a Conference, Organisation of a Workshop, Exhibition, Training, Participation to a Conference, Participation to a Workshop; Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop, Brokerage Event, Pitch Event, Trade Fair, Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)

Output:

Press release, Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication), Podcast, Flyer, Social Media, Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV), Video/Film

** **Outreach:** No. of participants, Social media reach/impressions

Means of verification:

Attendance lists, Meeting minutes, Photos, Statistics (website analytics and social media metrics/reach), Report, Links

Whenever a partner dedicates efforts/resources to contribute to and drive forward the project's outreach strategy, the tracker collates their actions to keep full traceability and collect relevant evidence towards the official reporting to the European Commission.

5.1.1 Work Package Meetings

The exploitation, dissemination, and communication activities for RAASCAMAN are managed under WP6 – Exploitation, Dissemination, and Communication. Regular work package meetings will play a critical role in ensuring the successful implementation and alignment of these activities with the overall project objectives.

Meeting Frequency and Purpose

- Monthly Meetings: Held at regular intervals to track progress, address challenges, and maintain alignment across consortium members.

- **Key Purposes:**
 - **Content Planning and Delivery:** Identify, plan, and deliver communication, dissemination, and exploitation materials, including updates on Key Exploitable Results (KERs), publications, events, and outreach activities.
 - **Monitoring Progress:** Evaluate the status of WP6 tasks, ensuring milestones are met and any deviations are identified and addressed.
 - **Exploitation Strategy Oversight:** Review strategies for leveraging exploitable assets and outcomes, ensuring maximum impact.
 - **Risk Management:** Address any risks or challenges arising from ongoing activities and define corrective actions or adjustments.
 - **Cross-Work Package Synergies:** Ensure that WP6 activities support and align with the deliverables of other work packages and the overarching goals of RAASCCEMAN.

Participants

- **Core Team:** WP6 leader and task coordinators responsible for specific activities within exploitation, dissemination, and communication.
- **Partner Representatives:** At least one representative from each RAASCCEMAN partner involved in WP6 tasks, ensuring diverse input and coordination.
- **Optional Participants:** Other consortium members may participate upon request or as required by the agenda.

Scope and Output

These meetings will ensure that RAASCCEMAN's exploitation strategy is robust, its dissemination efforts are impactful and far-reaching, and its communication activities effectively engage all target audiences. The discussions will also facilitate the smooth delivery of WP6 deliverables and foster collaboration across partners for maximizing the project's results and outreach.

Conclusion

The Dissemination and Communication Plan for the RAASCCEMAN project outlines a comprehensive and strategic approach to ensure the effective dissemination of the project's innovative solutions to key stakeholders across both scientific and industrial communities. RAASCCEMAN's AI-driven tools and solutions, designed to optimize supply chains, enhance resilience, and improve manufacturing processes, will benefit a wide range of industries, including automotive, bike manufacturing, and interconnected pilot lines.

By targeting industrial stakeholders, research communities, policy makers, and the general public, the plan leverages a variety of communication channels, from digital content to participation in industry events and workshops. A clear focus on community-driven dissemination through strategic partnerships with networks like EDIH, AI-based initiatives, and European NoEs, ensures RAASCCEMAN's visibility and broad engagement with relevant innovation ecosystems.

Through the creation of tailored showcase materials, including online information packages for each pilot use case, RAASCCEMAN will effectively demonstrate its real-world applications and impact. Social media campaigns and user stories will further highlight the project's success stories and tangible outcomes, facilitating understanding and interest across diverse audiences.

Due to the release of this document in the early stages of the project and the ever-changing nature of innovation, both communication and dissemination actions might be subject to modifications throughout the project's lifespan. Therefore, this can be considered a living document, and any changes will be adequately reflected in successive iterations of upcoming updates – either as internal updates of C&D planning or within the relevant WP6 deliverables.

Annex I: Logo and Visual Identity

The visual identity of RAASCCEMAN represents the corporate design of the project. The consistent application and publication of these elements across various communication channels ensure a uniform appearance of RAASCCEMAN. This leads to the creation of a high level of recognition, which is essential for brand development. Equally important is that the corporate design should not only be communicated externally but should also be implemented in internal communication. This contributes to the project members identifying more strongly with the project and carrying the image of RAASCCEMAN into external interactions as well.

Corporate design is the foundation of the broader corporate identity and serves as a cornerstone for brand building. The elements of the visual identity, such as the logo, color palette, typography, and other assets, are key in establishing a consistent and recognizable brand presence.

Logo

The RAASCCEMAN logo is designed to be both functional and meaningful. It is the first thing people will see when they encounter the project, and its job is to make an immediate, lasting impression. The logo comes in several versions, each tailored to different uses, ensuring that it always appears in the best possible way no matter the medium.

- **Primary Logo Variant:** The horizontal logo is the most versatile. Its clean and balanced design makes it perfect for use in website headers, email signatures, and any other primary placements where the brand needs to be prominently displayed. This version sets the tone for RAASCCEMAN's visual identity, combining clarity with a touch of sophistication.
- **Secondary Logo Variant:** The vertical logo variant provides a more attention-grabbing design. This version is ideal for contexts where the project needs to make a strong impact, whether on banners, promotional materials, or event signage. It's designed to command attention and leave a lasting impression.
- **Logo Symbol:** The simplified RAASCCEMAN symbol offers flexibility in situations where the full logo might not be appropriate or where space is limited. It can be used as a favicon, social media profile picture, or even as a standalone visual identifier in smaller formats. Despite its simplicity, the symbol remains instantly recognizable as part of the broader RAASCCEMAN brand.
- **Dark Logo Variant:** The dark logo is specifically designed for use in situations where the primary logo would be too hard to see against certain backgrounds. It maintains the integrity of the design while ensuring maximum visibility, making it suitable for darker themes or backgrounds with lots of visual noise.

- **White Logo Variant:** On darker or more vibrant backgrounds, the white logo variant offers a clean, sharp contrast that makes the logo stand out. This version ensures legibility and consistency across a variety of different contexts, from presentations to marketing materials.

The clear space around the logo is another crucial aspect of maintaining its visibility and impact. This space is essential for ensuring that the logo doesn't get crowded by other elements, allowing it to breathe and stand out on its own. The full guidelines for logo usage and clear space are detailed in the annex.

Graphic Elements and Colour Palette

RAASCAMAN Typography

Typography is a critical element of any visual identity, and for RAASCAMAN, the chosen typefaces are modern, readable, and designed to complement the project's high-tech nature. The fonts have been selected to provide clarity and readability across both print and digital mediums, ensuring that the message is always communicated effectively.

- **Object Sans:** The RAASCAMAN logo is set in Object Sans, a sleek, contemporary typeface that conveys the forward-thinking nature of the project. This typeface is clean, modern, and functional, aligning with the technological focus of RAASCAMAN while remaining highly legible.
- **Sora:** For all online and printed materials, the Sora typeface is used. Available through Google Fonts, Sora offers versatility and readability, with its clean and geometric design making it ideal for both headers and body text. Sora Bold is used for titles and headings, providing emphasis where needed, while Sora Regular ensures that body text is easy to read and digest.

These typographic choices help establish a modern, professional tone for RAASCAMAN, ensuring that all communications—whether digital or printed—are clear and engaging.

RAASCAMAN Color Palette

The RAASCAMAN color palette is built to reflect the project's cutting-edge technological nature while maintaining a professional and trustworthy appearance. Each color was chosen not only for its visual appeal but also for its symbolic meaning within the context of Industry 4.0.

Primary Blue #102C47

Secondary #1B567C

Teal #32B9B4

- **Primary Blue (#102C47):** The deep, professional blue is the anchor of the RAASCAMAN visual identity. It represents trust, stability, and expertise, qualities that are essential in a project dealing with advanced technologies and innovation. This color is used for key elements like headlines and important graphics, ensuring that RAASCAMAN commands attention without overwhelming the viewer.
- **Secondary Blue (#1B567C):** The secondary blue shade complements the primary blue and adds depth to the palette. This color is used for body text, background elements, and as a filter for project images. It's a versatile, understated color that helps create a balanced visual hierarchy and ensures that important content stands out.

- Teal (#32B9B4): Teal is a vibrant, dynamic accent color that injects energy into the design. It is used sparingly to highlight key information, such as calls to action or important details. The brightness of teal contrasts with the deeper blues, drawing the viewer's eye to specific areas of the design, making them stand out in an otherwise structured layout.

The combination of these colors creates a visual identity that is both modern and professional, allowing RAASCEMAN to stand out while maintaining a sense of authority and trustworthiness. These colors are flexible enough to be adapted to various materials and platforms, from digital screens to print media.

Annex II: Key Communication Messages

Key Messaging Themes

- *Manufacturing as a Service (MaaS)* – Positioning MaaS as a transformative approach to enhancing supply chain resilience and flexibility, creating a strong market advantage for adopters.
- *AI and Robotics for Real-World Challenges* – Promoting the practical applicability of RAASCCEMAN solutions in addressing real-world manufacturing challenges.
- *Collaborative Innovation* – Highlighting RAASCCEMAN’s partnerships and multi-disciplinary approach as key enablers of success.
- *Optimized Productivity and Capacity Utilization* – A MaaS network combined with better planning and scheduling software in the factory level allows to increase productivity and use of the open capacity. It will also increase transparency leading to new customers for the manufacturing companies.
- *New Business Models and Revenue Streams* – The MaaS business model, enabled by the project's solutions, can allow manufacturers to expand their offerings beyond traditional products and services and generate new revenue streams by providing a range of value-added services to their customers.
- *Manufacturing Transformation and Sustainability* – A unique opportunity to transform the manufacturing sector, reduce costs, increase output, and enhance sustainability.

Target Audience	Examples of RAASCCEMAN Messages
Industrial Manufacturers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "RAASCCEMAN empowers your company with tools to quickly adapt to supply chain disruptions, reducing delays and enhancing competitiveness." • "Through our MaaS network, gain access to alternative suppliers and dynamic scheduling to keep your production lines running smoothly, even in the face of unforeseen events." • "Improve your supply chain’s resilience with real-time, actionable data that helps you make better, faster decisions when disruptions occur."
Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Manufacturing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "RAASCCEMAN helps SMEs overcome the challenges of limited suppliers by recommending alternative sources for materials, ensuring business continuity." • "By leveraging circularity, RAASCCEMAN enables you to find remanufactured goods as a local procurement alternative, improving sustainability and reducing costs." • "Reduce the costs and effort of managing small batch productions with RAASCCEMAN’s dynamic planning and scheduling capabilities."
System Integrators and Technology Providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "RAASCCEMAN offers a seamless integration of MaaS technologies into existing production environments, ensuring scalability and adaptability in modern manufacturing ecosystems." • "By implementing RAASCCEMAN’s dynamic scheduling and automated supply chain tools, you can streamline production workflows and enhance factory resilience to supply chain disruptions." • "Be part of advancing supply chain integration with innovative technologies that facilitate cross-company data exchange and enhance the flexibility of European manufacturing systems."
Software and Application Developers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "With RAASCCEMAN, you can contribute to the next generation of software tools that empower manufacturers to make data-driven decisions and adapt to supply chain disruptions." • "Develop advanced applications that leverage machine learning, semantic matching, and Bayesian inference to predict and mitigate risks across the supply chain." • "Help build intuitive interfaces and tools that bridge the gap between complex industrial data and actionable insights, improving the decision-making process in real time."

Target Audience	Examples of RAASCCEMAN Messages
<p>Supply Chain Managers and Decision Makers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "With RAASCCEMAN’s intelligent recommendation engine, you can optimize your supply chain operations, ensuring faster response times to disruptions." • "Our automated tools allow you to predict and quantify disruptions, making it easier to decide when to switch suppliers or adapt your production schedules." • "RAASCCEMAN’s solutions provide you with a dynamic, data-driven approach to manage both short-term and medium-term supply chain risks."
<p>Research Institutions and Scientific Community</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "RAASCCEMAN introduces advanced technologies like Bayesian inference networks and semantic matching to dynamically optimize supply chain resilience." • "Our project is at the forefront of MaaS, enabling self-adaptation in manufacturing networks and supporting European industries in becoming more resilient." • "Join us in advancing the field of supply chain and manufacturing resilience with the application of next-generation technologies and solutions."
<p>Policy Makers and Industry Regulators</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "RAASCCEMAN supports European manufacturing in achieving sustainability and climate neutrality goals by providing resilient, agile supply chain solutions." • "By enabling circularity and localized production alternatives, RAASCCEMAN contributes to reducing the dependency on global supply chains, making the EU manufacturing sector more robust." • "The RAASCCEMAN project provides evidence-based solutions that help European manufacturers respond to geopolitical risks and supply chain challenges efficiently."

Annex III: Obligatory Publicity and Acknowledgement

Funding Statement

Based on the Article 17 of the GA, communication activities (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement:

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Additionally, to that, it is also possible to add following sentence: This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreements No. 101138782.

Acknowledgement

For the purposes of the scientific acknowledgement, in case of scientific and other result (i.e. as a part of the publication when registered or submitted) following acknowledgement shall be used:

This work was supported by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under the RAASCAMAN Project (Resilient and Adaptive Supply Chains for Capability-based Manufacturing as a Service Networks), grant agreement No. 101138782.

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Annex IV: Initial Planning 2025: List of Events and Conferences

Topic-relevant events for the presentation of the project's outcomes to the European innovation ecosystem:

Title of event/activity	Description	Partner	Timing	Type of participation
Hannover Fair	The world's leading industrial trade show, showcasing innovations in automation, digitalization, energy solutions, and advanced Manufacturing.	DFKI	March/ April 2025 31.03. - 4.04.2025	Presentation of the project in individual talks with visitors at the DFKI booth
All Hands Meeting of the German AI Competence Centers	An annual meeting bringing together German leading five university-based AI competence centres to discuss advancements in AI research and foster collaboration	DFKI	September/ October 2025 Two-day event	Presentation of a poster at a network meeting of science and politics (approx. 250 participants)
International Engineering Fair in Brno, CZ (MSV Brno)	Central Europe's leading industrial trade fair, focusing on engineering, automation, and cutting-edge manufacturing technologies.	CIIRC CTU	October 2025 (every year)	Presentation of the use cases at the stage and at the joint booth together with industrial stakeholders
Open Day for Industry 4.0 in Prague	Annual event co-organised with the National Centre for Industry 4.0 mainly for industrial stakeholders and policy makers	CIIRC CTU	May/June 2025 & 2026 (every year)	Presentation of use cases; hands-on workshop
Hands-on workshops with EDIH CTU and the Czech node of AI-MATTERS	Practical workshop for representatives of companies and their technical staff.	CIIRC CTU	tbc	Demonstration of use cases directly in the Prague testbed
RealizeLIVE 2025/ Conference	Siemens' premier digital transformation conference, bringing together professionals in engineering, manufacturing, and product lifecycle management to share insights and explore the latest trends and technologies.	Conti	June/July 2025	Presentation – Continental as a speaker on RealizeLIVE in Amsterdam will present GLN activities in BDY and RAASCAMAN will be part of the future steps.a
Flemish event by VIL (logistics institute)	Event for companies showing how digitization is accelerating the transformation to a sustainable economy.	FM	February 2025	Presentation on the digital product passport for the ASKA case

Scientific dissemination - Selected conferences in the pipeline for 2025

Title of conference	Description	Partner	Timing	Type of participation
RAAD 2025, Belgrade	34 th International Conference on Robotics in Alpe-Adria-Danube region. https://raad2025.etf.bg.ac.rs/	DFKI	18 – 20 June 2025	Paper presentation (paper has been submitted)
ETFA 2025, Porto	IEEE International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation. https://etfa2025.ieee-ies.org/	DFKI	9 – 12 September 2025	Paper presentation (the paper is currently in preparation)